

A STUDY ON EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICE ON LUNG CAPACITY IN ORPHANAGE FEMALES

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Abstract

During recent years, a lot of research work has been done to show the beneficial effects of yoga training. The present study was undertaken to assess the effects of yogic practice on some pulmonary functions. Sixty orphanage female subjects (age group 13-18yrs.) were selected. They had to do the yogic practices daily for about one hour. The observations were recorded by MEDSPIROR, in the form of FVC, FEV-1 and PEFR on day-1, after 6 weeks and 12 weeks of their yogic practice. There was significant increase in FVC, FEV-1 and PEFR at the end of 12 weeks.

Keywords: *Yogic exercises, FVC, FEV-1, PEFR*

Introduction

Yoga is a great gift to mankind which helps us keep better and maintain our health. You also develop a higher patience level when you practice yoga which also helps in keeping the negative thoughts away. You get great mental clarity and better understanding. In short, yoga has several benefits. It brings together physical and mental disciplines to achieve a peaceful body and mind; it helps manage stress and anxiety and keeps you relaxing. It also helps in increasing flexibility, muscle strength and body tone. It improves respiration, energy and vitality.

Medical science tries to achieve an optimum physical and mental health of the individual through preventive, curative and promotive means. However, for a long time medical professionals have laid much emphasis on the curative aspect and only relatively recently the preventive aspect is also being emphasized whereas in yogic practice the stress is mainly on the promotive aspect, although some yogic methods are prescribed for curative purposes as well. A number of studies have been done to assess the effect of yogic practice on FVC FEV-1 PEFR pulmonary functions. Udupa et al studied the effects of some breathing exercises (Pranayam) in normal persons. Nayar et al documented the effects of yogic exercises on human physical efficiency. In

another study, oxygen consumption during three yoga-breathing patterns was shown by Miles Wales. In a related work, Makwana et al studied the effects of short term yoga practice on Ventilatory Function Tests. The present study has been done exclusively on young healthy females to add more data in the field of yoga and pulmonary functions. This study has been designed to explain and ascertain the promotive aspects of health and yoga. By practising yoga, one can deal with several challenges, including stress and physical ailments. Yoga helps make muscles flexible, reduces weight, and also improves the health of the skin. Yoga helps develop patience and concentration, sharpens memory and brings peace into our lives.

Yoga is a way of life and if we incorporate yoga in our life slowly and make it an integral part of our life, we would be in a peaceful state in our everyday life. We would be able to take decisions without getting clouded by our emotions. We would think and act with complete attention, focus and awareness. 'Stress' is a buzzword of the modern world. And stress has become an acceptable way of life today, which is surely not at all good for our physical and mental health. Yoga seeks to replace this stress with calmness and peace. That's the importance of Yoga. Yoga opens up the blockages at our mind, body, breath and emotions level and takes us to a much higher plane of living. The yogic way of life ensures that every situation is not viewed as stress and the body is not always in the flight or fight mode. Yoga paves the way for the rejuvenation, rest and growth of our body.

At the physical level, yoga asana seeks to remove blockages and rigidity and build strength over a period of time. Asana seeks to create new body patterns which enables the body to operate at its potential best by removing all impurities.

At the breath level, pranayama seeks to extend our breath so that prana or the life force, is not dissipated and slowly converges inside our body leading to a high level of positive, clear state of mind. At the foundation of our daily life are the principles of Yama and Niyama which enable us to live harmoniously with others and our own selves. The principles of nonviolence, truth, non-stealing, purity, non-greed, contentment, self-study, surrendering to a higher being all result in us having congenial relations with people around us. And this paves the way for a peaceful state of mind.

Over a period of time, the deeper practice of meditation brings in complete clarity and calmness and enables one to step back from momentary pleasures and seek a deeper truth which would bring in the lasting joy and bliss. Yoga in our daily lives brings in greater harmony in our thoughts, deeds and actions. Yoga is all about being kind to others and to our own selves. It eliminates the very often vein of judging people harshly or unfairly. It brings down the agitation and restlessness in us and sets us on the path of a calm, meaningful and focused way of living.

Importance of Yoga

Man is a physical, mental and spiritual being; yoga helps promote a balanced development of all the three.

Yogic practices recharge the body and mind with cosmic energy and facilitate:

- Attainment of perfect equilibrium and harmony
- Promotes self-healing
- It's detox body and mind
- Enhances the body and mind strength
- Increases self-awareness
- Increase concentration
- Decrease stress, anxiety, depression and tension in the physical body by activating the parasympathetic nervous system

The aspirant feels rejuvenated and energized. Thus, yoga bestows upon every aspirant the powers to control body and mind.

Benefits of Yoga

1. Yoga helps you in all-around fitness

Some very discernible ones are:

- Improves health
- Gives mental strength
- Improves physical strength
- Protects from injury
- Detoxifies the body

2. Yoga benefits in weight loss

Suryanamaskar and kapalbhatti pranayama are highly useful for losing weight. Moreover, with regular practice of yoga, we tend to become more sensitive to our body and its needs. This, in turn, helps keep a check on our food intake and body weight.

3. Yoga is one of the best solutions for stress relief

A few minutes of yoga daily can be a great way to get rid of stress, both in body and mind. Asana, pranayama, and meditation are effective techniques to release stress.

4. Yoga helps for inner peace

We all love to visit peaceful, serene spots that are rich in natural beauty. Little do we realize that peace can be found right within us and we can take a mini vacation to experience this any time of the day. Yoga is also one of the best ways to calm the disturb mind and body.

5. Yoga Improves Immunity

Our system is a seamless blend of the body, mind, and spirit. An irregularity in the body affects the mind and similarly, unpleasantness or restlessness in the mind can manifest as an ailment in the body. Yoga asana help massage organs and strengthens muscles while breathing techniques and meditation release stress and improve immunity.

6. Yoga improves relationships

Yoga can even help improve your relationship with your loved ones. A mind that is relaxed, happy and content is better able to deal with sensitive relationship matters. Yoga and meditation aids in keeping the mind happy and peaceful. Gradually, you will also notice an improvement in your relations with those around you.

7. Yoga Increases Energy

Do you feel completely drained by the end of the day? Shuttling through chores and multitasking continuously can be quite exhausting. A few minutes of yoga every day boosts our energy level and keeps us fresh.

8. Yoga Gives you Better Flexibility and Posture

Yoga must become a part of your daily routine to get a body that is strong and flexible. Regular yoga practice stretches and tones the body muscles and also makes them strong. It also helps improve your body posture when you stand, sit, sleep or walk. This would, in turn, help relieve you of body ache due to incorrect posture.

Methods

The study was carried out at Studies for Department of Social Security in Annai Sathiyammayar Ninaivu Government Orphan Home Cuddalore District. Total 209 females in orphanage home but I am selected this paper only 60 girls only selected for this paper. 60 orphanage girls students volunteered as subjects and their physical characteristics like height, weight and age, which have a role to play in determining the lung volumes, have been given in Table I.

All the subjects used to do yoga practice daily for about one hour. The yogic schedule consisted of a prayer, asanas, pranayam and meditation. The exercise regimen included different yogic asanas viz : Padmasana, Yoga Mudra, Matsyasana, Kukkudasan, Uthana Padhasana, Pavanmuktasana, Paschimotasana; Dhanurasana, Supta Vajrasana, Gomukhasana, Viparita Karani, Sarvangasana, Halasan, Karna Peedasana, Bhujangasana, Bakasana, Mandukasana, Parvathasana, N auli and Shavasana. Optionally the subjects could do cleansing procedures (kriya) also.

All the subjects had to do pranayam essentially for about 10 to 15 minutes. Pranayam schedule included the deep breathing, inhalation-retention-exhalation at fixed intervals, abdominal (diaphragmatic) breathing and alternate nostril breathing.

The subjects performing yoga less than 5 days a week were also not included in the study. *Pulmonary Function Tests (PFT)* were recorded by MEDSPIROR - made in India (Chandigarh)- a computerized dry type spirometer. The parameters of PFT included in the study were - FVC (Forced vital capacity), FEVI (Forced expiratory volume in 1st second) and PEFV (Peak expiratory flow rate). Recordings were done on day-1, after 6 weeks and after 12 weeks of yogic practice. Day-1 means the very first day the subjects started yogic practice: For PFT - the subjects were first explained the whole procedure and were demonstrated the same after obtaining their consent. The subjects performed the test in sitting position.

Statistical Analysis

The results of PFT (Pulmonary Function Tests) are presented as mean \pm S.D. The data were analyzed using student's 't' test. P values <0.05 were considered significant.

TABLE I: Physical characteristics of subjects

	Mean	Median	SD
Age Group (Years)	22.7	22.5	3.61
Height (cms)	155.3	156	4.917
Weight (kgs)	55.9	56	7.49

TABLE II: Comparison of lung function tests

Time interval	FVC (lit)	FEV-1 (lit)	PEFR (lit / sec)
/ Parameter	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD
Day-1	2.02 \pm 0.29	1.99 \pm 0.29	5.10 \pm 1.12
Weeks-6	2.27 \pm 0.28*	2.24 \pm 0.28*	5.34 \pm 1.10**
Weeks-12	2.54 \pm 0.27*	2.50 \pm 0.27*	5.59 \pm 1.09***

*P<0.001 **P =N.S. ***P<0.05

In this study, FVC and FEV -1 were significantly higher at weeks-6 and weeks-12 from day-1 (P<0.001). However, PEFR is not statistically significant at weeks-6 but value of PEFR is higher at weeks-6 in comparison to day-I. At weeks-12, PEFR is significantly higher than day-1 (P<0.05).

Makwana et al reported significant increase in FVC following 10 weeks of yoga training. Others have recorded similar observations. The improvement in vital capacity is due in part to increased development of respiratory musculature incidental to regular practice of yogic exercise. By the practice the respiratory apparatus is emptied and filled more completely and efficiently which is recorded in terms of increased FVC.

Similar ventilatory training even in elderly subjects (age 60 to 75 yrs) has been shown to improve lung volumes and capacities. Makwana et al also showed increased FEV-1 after 10 weeks of yogic practice. The increase in FEV-1 might be due to significant increase in vital capacity. Joshi et al reported significant increase in FVC and PEFr following 6 weeks of pranayam practice.

Lung inflation near to total lung capacity is a major physiological stimulus for the release of lung surfactant and prostaglandins into alveolar spaces, which increase lung compliance and decreases bronchial smooth muscle tone respectively. The other possible mechanism for improved PFT may be:

1. Increased power of respiratory muscles that is due to the work hypertrophy of the muscles during pranayam and other exercises.
2. Cleansing procedures cleans the infective nasal secretions.
3. Yogic breathing exercises train practitioners to use the diaphragmatic and abdominal muscles more efficiently thereby emptying and filling the respiratory apparatus more efficiently and completely.
4. Yoga, with its calming effect on the mind can reduce and release emotional stresses, thereby withdrawing the broncho-constrictor effect.

Thus, practice of yogic exercises seems to be beneficial for respiratory efficiency. A number of studies have been done to show the beneficial effects of yoga on asthmatic patients. In recent studies, effect of yoga on ventilatory responses, respiratory endurance and muscle strength have been well documented. Bera et al have studied 'recovery from stress by yogic relaxation posture' in their recent work.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be stated that yogic exercises are beneficial for the better maintenance of body functions, particularly pulmonary functions, even in normal healthy subjects. In our study, there was significant increase in FVC, FEV-1 and PEFr at the end of 12 weeks of yogic practice in young healthy orphanage females.

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